

The PlaceConcept Methodology: A Technique to Investigate Place-Based Emotions

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Abstract

Human emotional responses to places are often intuitive and difficult to vocalize, but people only thrive in spaces that meet their emotional needs. The PlaceConcept methodology, which is firmly rooted in psychology's phenomenological tradition, comprehensively elicits user (or potential user) emotion-based assessments of existing and proposed spaces. It captures emotion and design related information important for the creation of spaces using a forced choice, image-based projective online tool. This technique differs from other image-based methodologies because it includes not only stimuli to measure general emotional response, but also items to assess place design criteria that influence emotional response to space (territoriality, sensory richness, privacy, restoration level, level of control, prospect and refuge, interpersonal density, and personal space). The tool has been utilized in both commercial and residential applications and found to be useful for understanding emotional response to places and for developing profiles of spaces that are immediately applicable.

Conference theme: Design & Emotion: Methodological Issues

Keywords: environment, image, online survey

Theoretical Basis of PlaceConcept Tool

Space design has a significant influence on human well-being, through its ability to affect us emotionally (Mehrabian, Russell, 1974). Homes, schools, offices, hospitals, outdoor plazas, and the myriad of other places experienced by human beings during the course of a day all matter emotionally. Research has shown that incorporating people into the design of the spaces they will use can improve place-based experience – if the concerns of users are addressed (Zeisel, 1981). The Place-Concept methodology recognizes the importance of emotional response to space and incorporates people into the design of the places they use.

Extensive research has shown that emotional responses to spaces and objects can be described using two continuums, one measuring pleasure and the other energy level (e.g., Russell, 1980) and the PlaceConcept tool captures responses to spaces along those axes. Other approaches can be used to describe emotional response to space, for example physiological response or stated emotional reaction. The system outlined by Russell and others is, however, the most appropriate basis for a remote assessment of complex, difficult to articulate, place-based experiences.

Places should satisfy a variety of basic human needs. Humans need a territory (which they can personalize to represent themselves), personal space (which changes configuration based on culture and situation), and shelter where they can restore their cognitive energy levels, for example (Gifford, 2007). Satisfaction of these place-specific needs is also probed with the PlaceConcept methodology. Investigation of these issues is important because of the emotional and cognitive repercussions of these design factors (e.g., Fredrickson, Branigan 2005; Isen, Johnson, Mertz, Robinson, 1985).

Fredrickson defines affect as “Present within emotions (as the component of subjective experience), it is also present within many other affective phenomena, including physical sensations, attitudes, moods, and even affective traits” (2001, p. 218). Others have used the term “affect” to refer to both mood and emotion (James, Brodersen, Eisenberg, 2004). This more general definition of “affect” is used here. Positive affect is usually defined as “pleasant feelings induced by commonplace events or circumstances” (Isen, Baron, 1991, p. 1) and the definition for negative affect is generally the reverse (Thoresen, Kaplan, Barsky, Warren, 2003).

Positive affect has been linked to broadened thinking/attention and thought-action repertoires, when compared to neutral or negative state processing (Fredrickson, Branigan, 2005). In general, positive affect has been positively related to: improved creative performance and increased innovation (Isen, Johnson, Mertz, Robinson, 1985); improved problem solving and decision making (Isen, 2001); more flexible, thorough, and efficient thinking on topics meaningful or interesting to the thinker (Isen, 2001); strategic thinking (Loken, 2006); constructive and cooperative bargaining, increased generosity, social responsibility, helping and interpersonal understanding (Isen, 2001); constructive suggestions (George, Brief, 1992); avoidance of real and meaningful risk (Isen, Johnson, Mertz, Robinson, 1985); and improved self-knowledge (Fredrickson, 2001). Positive emotions can help build durable personal resources such as physical skills or health, social resources such as friendships and networks, intellectual resources such as knowledge, and psychological resources such as optimism (Fredrickson, Branigan, 2005). Early research indicated that positive affect might lead to decreased cognitive capacity or motivation to process information systematically, but more recent evidence has indicated the opposite effect (Isen, 2001).

Negative affect also clearly relates to knowledge worker behavior. In addition to not exhibiting the linkages noted above for positive affect, it encourages thorough, analytical, detail-oriented, systematic thinking, but in more focused areas and narrower thought-action repertoires than in a neutral state (Cote, 1999; Fredrickson, Branigan, 2005). Brief and Weiss (2002) report that negative affect in the workplace has been linked to negative interpersonal interactions, anxiety, more extreme emotions after negative work experiences, and reduced positive response to positive workplace events. Negative affect and positive affect are not necessarily related to inverse patterns of mental processing, behaviors, etc. (Isen, Baron, 1991).

Affect can be environmentally induced. Aspects of places, such as floor plans and lighting levels can lead to positive and negative moods among people in those spaces (e.g., Cooper, 1976; Isen, Baron, 1991; Mehrabian, Russell, 1974). For example, positive affect can be generated through environmental factors, such as smells (Baron, 1990). Baron found that individuals experiencing a pleasant scent exhibited behaviors consistent with positive affect (Baron, 1990). There are many other demonstrations of environmentally induced positive affect in the literature related not only to smells, but

also to social density, lighting levels, level of enclosure, and interpersonal distancing, for example (Isen, Baron, 1991). Places that are consistent with users' psychological needs for a territory, sensory richness, privacy, restoration, environmental control, refuge, interpersonal density, and personal space also encourage positive affect states (Gifford, 2007). In general, positive affect ensues when an environment provides the sort of sensory experiences that are consistent with advantageous events during humans' evolutionary past or culturally and psychosocially desirable conditions. The use planned for a space often makes positive affect appropriate.

It is also important to design spaces that are consistent with people's psychological and physiological needs because this consistency reduces environmental stress (Evans, 1982). Environmental stress results when people are experiencing too much or too little sensory stimulation or when they are sitting too close to others, for example. Environmentally induced stress leads to negative affect (Isen, Baron, 1991; Mehrabian, Russell, 1974; Zeisel, 1981). When people experience environmental stress they are thus less likely to engage fully in desired activities, whether they be interpersonal or cognitive (e.g., Cote, 1999). By eliciting information on space design criteria that influence levels of environmental stress, the PlaceConcept methodology generates information that can be applied to create optimal places.

Individuals intuitively understand the sorts of spaces that will optimize their place-based experiences (Cooper, 1976). They can individually perform the complicated mental gymnastics required to conceptualize the appropriate space design for a person with their personality, working within their national and organizational culture, etc. While they understand at a nonverbal level the design of an appropriate space, they often do not have the vocabulary to discuss the appropriate design criteria (Marcus, 1995). They know the feelings that they should have in an optimally designed space, and can recognize those feelings when they are presented to them in images (Groat, Wang, 2002).

The PlaceConcept Methodology

Phenomenological and projective research tools have been used extensively in psychological research and they are the foundation for the PlaceConcept methodology. Place experience is highly subjective (Gifford, 2007), and phenomenological approaches are "focused on revealing the purely subjective aspects of consciousness" (Kendler, 2005,

p. 318) with the “goal of understanding the complex world of lived experience from the point of view of those who live it” (Schwandt, 1998, p. 221). Norberg-Schulz’s use of phenomenology to study the experience of being in built environments shows that phenomenological methodologies are applicable to place design (Norberg-Schulz, 1991).

The PlaceConcept tool probes holistic place experiences, and it does so within a cognitive structure imposed by the participant, not by the researcher. It investigates the “lived world” (Wertz, 2005, p. 169). Although the researcher supplies images used as stimuli, the pictures are ambiguous enough on non-pertinent details to accommodate the mental place concepts in use by participants. The images become metaphors that convey deep-seated nonverbal thoughts and feelings (Zaltman, 2003). The PlaceConcept tool builds on the tradition of minimally intrusive phenomenological interviews (Osborne, 1994), providing an opportunity for individuals to detail a place-based experience through the selection of images that they find appropriate.

When projective methodologies are used they are “less obvious in intent and therefore presumably less subject to faking . . . the structure imposed by the respondent is a reflection, or projection of his or her individual perceptions of the world” (Aiken, 1997, pp. 330-331). People who are not design professionals often lack the knowledge, and even the vocabulary to discuss place-related issues, and projective techniques have the added advantage of being useful when people are unable to provide verbal answers to questions (Soley, Smith, 2008).

The PlaceConcept methodology presents a pair of photographs electronically, via the Internet, to study participants; participants respond to multiple image pairs before completing the online survey. It can be used or as part of a multi-method research program. Each pair of images differs on an attribute of interest to environmental designers and participants must select one image from each pair before they are able to respond to the next pair. A paper-based software simulation is also available.

Participants chose the image presented that describes the experience that they have in an existing space, would prefer to have in a space under development, or anticipate in space that is described to them. Participants are charged with selecting the image that gives them the same emotional feeling as the space being investigated (which may be an ideal space of a particular type, e.g. ideal kitchen), whether the space is a residential,

commercial, retail, academic, or healthcare space. This sort of forced choice question is appropriate, because context-based responses to place are rarely ambivalent (Groat, Wang, 2002).

The use of the Internet to administer the tool means that more people can participate in any place-based study, and research can be conducted more efficiently, than if each participant was interviewed personally. It is also possible that information can be collected from individuals who could not be visited by the researcher because of practical considerations. The methodology has the added advantage of allowing participants to describe the experience of being in a place while they are actually in that place, as long as Internet access is available there. Insights derived from conversations with participants are lost, however, when the tool is administered via the Internet.

The PlaceConcept stimuli can also be used as the basis for a discussion when they are administered in paper format.

The images used by the PlaceConcept tool differ in fundamental ways on parameters of interest to place-based researchers. For example, two images of a field, one with, and one without a fence can be presented to participants to illicit feelings related to territoriality. Images of still or rushing water can be used to collect information about energy level. An image with an individual chair in a woodland and an image with two facing chairs in a woodland distinguish levels of privacy desired. The topics probed with the image pairs include perceptions of energy level, pleasantness, territoriality/personalization, sensory richness, privacy/socializing/distraction, restoration provided by a space, level of environmental control, refuge level, interpersonal density, and personal space. The design issues probed with the PlaceConcept tool are the aspects of the physical environment that most consistently have a significant influence on the psychological experience of being in a space. Research by environmental psychologists has shown that these topics can be independently discussed, but when these place-design attributes are combined they create complex space-based experiences.

Study participants are also asked demographic and space use related questions as needed to respond to the research question. Individuals are generally asked about their gender, age, profession, and national culture. The other questions that they are asked vary from

project to project. They could relate to specific attributes of their current homes, if the design of a residential space is being considered, for example.

A stringent development protocol was followed to select the images presented to participants. Photos in the 75 image pairs that are part of the PlaceConcept stimulus stable have been discussed face-to-face with participants in previous place design related projects over the course of several years. Researchers have access to an assortment of image pairs, representing the different concepts of concern, which can be presented to study participants. Typically 50 image pairs are selected for presentation. Several sample image pairs are included in an appendix to this document.

Studies using the PlaceConcept methodology are exploratory; they do not begin with a stringent hypothesis. Participants are free to paint whatever emotional picture of a space they desire, through their selection of images. Image pairs are included as stimuli based on the research question. For example, if the sensory richness of a space under development is of particular concern, more related images can be presented to study participants so that the issue can be fully addressed. Energy level might be an issue with the design of a kitchen, for example – should that space be more of a high-energy launch pad or a relaxation zone? Energy levels might be studied in some workplaces and not others, for example. Performance of a complex cognitive task will deteriorate in space that provides lots of environmental inputs to users, but it might be unclear what the user experienced task complexity level is, so the appropriate environmental input level for a new space could be probed in the context of users' current job responsibilities. Similarly, if theory indicates that a place should be pleasant, for example, fewer images probing the desired pleasantness of a space need to be presented. Participant responses to each of the image pairs related to a particular issue (such as energy level) are recorded and subscale scores are calculated. Some images related to each of the environmental parameters available for study are presented to participants in each study.

Patterns in responses to images are determined during the analysis phase. This process is very similar to the work that takes place after a multi-dimensional scaling plot is created, although no multi-dimensional scaling protocols are used in the PlaceConcept process. Interpreting the configuration produced through multi-dimensional scaling has been described as “examining the configuration to discover underlying patterns that are based on what one knows about the items” (Stalans, 1998, p. 147). When PlaceConcept data

are being analyzed, collections of subscale values are assessed until patterns emerge. Assessing information related to energy level, pleasure, territoriality, sensory richness, privacy, restoration level, level of control, prospect and refuge, interpersonal density, and personal space collected with the image pairs results in a rich place profile. A kitchen design study, which collected data via a paper-based PlaceConcept software simulation, determined, for example, that although a significant number of people in a particular geographic area prefer production oriented kitchen “workshops” where meals are created, the majority prefer that a cozy, family-private area for socializing be the focus of their kitchen space. These groups thus differed on their concepts of the appropriate role for this space (space-role). The first group of kitchen users might be seen as Food Technicians while the second set seen as Cozy Cookers.

Identification of subgroups in this way produces a more nuanced view of respondents, and is more consistent with the exploratory nature of the research conducted, than sophisticated statistical analyses of the data. However, the creation of subscales, as described above, does make these analyses possible. When entire collections of data are assessed, scale averages, etc., start to converge on their midpoints, etc., and the rich insights available in the data are lost. For example, when the kitchen related data (mentioned above) from the response set of approximately 50 people were compared to a data set of approximately equal size generated during a workstation design project (also collected using a paper-based software simulation) whose participants were fundamentally similar to those of the kitchen design project (young professionals of the same racial and cultural background as the people in the first study and living in the same region of the United States), few differences were observed in the design criteria for home spaces and work spaces. The data analysis revealed that environmental control was more important in the workplace environment while it was important for kitchens to be private, restorative refuges that are not as sensorially rich as the workplace. When patterns in the data collected were assessed, however, not only did the space-roles discussed above emerge regarding kitchens, but so did intriguing workplace space-roles. Sensation-intense, high energy thought factories surfaced as a relatively popular design option among a significant number of workplace project participants, but a sizable group desired low energy “retreat” workplaces, for example. These informative nuances were missed in the group level discussions of material gathered.

The fast-paced PlaceConcept methodology explores significant, often subtle, issues in a format that engages study participants. It is difficult to provide socially (or personally) desirable responses during the image selection process.

A database of cumulative responses from all studies conducted to date is available for comprehensive, cross-place analyses. The database uses an Excel format and data can be selected for study based on space type, user demographics, and responses to specific images, for example.

No images of the type of place being studied are used during any project (i.e., no pictures of classrooms during a school design project), so that the discussion remains at an abstract level. Maintaining this abstract level of discussion insures that individual designers have the freedom to interpret the information collected.

In return for participation, PlaceConcept delivers a brief “place personality profile” to participating individuals that describes some of their specific place-related design needs. This profile is feasible when individuals describe, at minimum, their ideal conception of the sort of space being developed and the survey is administered electronically. The brief profile is based the images selected, and reviews two aspects of personality that have been shown to have a relationship to place experience: locus of control (the extent to which people feel they control their own destiny) and introversion/extraversion (whether people primarily focus on their external or internal worlds) (Friedman, Schustack, 2006; Juhasz, Paxson, 1978; Little, 1987). These technical personality terms are not used in the profile.

A sample profile is: “When describing your ideal X [place], you have generally selected images that have rectilinear (straight, not curved) elements and you seem to prefer environments in which you receive a lot of sensory stimulation. People who prefer rectilinear shapes generally enjoy being in places that they can modify as they see fit, by moving the furniture around, etc. Make sure that spaces you create for yourself are easy to change. Often people who want to receive lots of stimulation through their environment focus on the world around themselves. Places where there is something for you to watch (such as people) are very interesting to you – so don’t plan on doing thoughtful work when you are around others.” Four versions of this message are available (internal or external locus of control AND introverted or extraverted).

The PlaceConcept methodology is a reliable and valid way to assess responses to experienced and imaged spaces that is largely language and culture independent. Reliability has been shown through internal consistency among item selections and the stability in responses shown during the image investigation period. Validity was determined through the content analysis of conversations with study participants that proceeded image selection. These conversations verified that images measure what they are stated to measure. Analyses of the data collected with the PlaceConcept methodology are based on theory and previous research done by people investigating the designs of products and places. Place designers have found the information supplied by the PlaceConcept methodology to be immediately applicable to design projects.

Appendix – Sample Image Pairs

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